

Principles of Aristotelian Modal Logic

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Abstract: The relationships between categorical propositions can be effectively represented through their possible truth value combinations. This paper integrates modern logical methods into the analysis of Aristotelian logic by employing adapted truth tables. While the semantics of modal extensions involves intricate relationships, we demonstrate that these tools are instrumental in clarifying them. By utilizing the truth tables, we systematically derive the specific conversion rules of Aristotle's logic, leading to a more coherent understanding of his modal propositions. This approach establishes a foundation for developing a formalized and consistent system of Aristotelian logic.

Keywords: Modal logic; Aristotelian logic; conversion principles; truth tables

1. Introduction

In the design of modern logical systems, accounting for edge cases is essential to ensure completeness, consistency, and the generality of proofs. In contrast, Aristotle's organizational approach in his writings—marked by extensive consideration of diverse cases and scenarios—often obscures the foundational principles of his logical theory. While his assertoric syllogistic is both consistent and syntactically complete within its scope (Bobzien, 2022: 2.4), the broad casuistry he employs can be disorienting. This approach frequently gives the impression that Aristotle does not prioritize minimizing interference or simplifying the initial stages of his investigations.

One notable edge case arises from Aristotle's consideration of terms that align closely with the modern concept of empty classes. He explores hypothetical scenarios in which the referents for his terms cease to exist and evaluates the truth of the resulting propositions (e.g., in *Prior Analytics* I.15, 34b11–13; 46, 51b36–52a14; II, 21, 67a9–21). However, when the idea of empty classes was introduced in the mathematization of syllogistic logic (Boole, 1854: 226–242), it was not extended to modal logic. Instead, it was limited to re-evaluating the validity of certain assertoric syllogisms.

Currently, most scholars assume that *all terms in Aristotelian syllogisms are non-empty* (Smith, 2022: 5.2; Łukasiewicz, 1957; Hintikka, 1973; Corcoran, 1974), although the issue remains controversial. The reasons for excluding empty terms are not merely a matter of simplicity. A coherent reconstruction of the foundations of Aristotle's logic must preserve its clearly established results. This approach does not entail ignoring that, in formulating universal categorical propositions, Aristotle tacitly admits that some compartments or subclasses are empty. In other words, rejecting empty terms in logical analysis does not preclude considering empty subclasses within broader categories.

Malink’s (2013) reconstruction of Aristotelian modal logic is among the most comprehensive, although its conceptual complexity makes it challenging to use as a basis for developing practical logical systems. Our approach simplifies Aristotelian logic, making it more amenable to modern logical methods. To better understand modal categorical propositions, we focus on analyzing their possible truth values.

We have avoided delving into intricate debates about the consistency of modal expressions between *Prior Analytics*—the primary focus of our work—and *On Interpretation*. Following Łukasiewicz (1957: 134), we use the terms “contingent” and “possible” as translations of *endechómenon* and *dynatón*, respectively, despite the contentious nature of their distinction.

In terms of notation, we use lowercase letters to denote the types of categorical propositions: universal affirmative (*a*), universal negative (*e*), particular affirmative (*i*), and particular negative (*o*). The terms of each proposition—predicate and subject—are represented with capital letters (*A* and *B*). Thus, we have the following abbreviations and their meanings: *AaB*, “A belongs to every B”; *AeB*, “A belongs to no B”; *AiB*, “A belongs to some B”; and *AoB*, “A does not belong to some B”.

By disregarding empty terms, the possible truth values for the categorical forms of proposition *AB* are reduced to the three rows in Table 1. This simplification avoids logical impossibilities in interpretation.

Table 1. Truth values of the categorical forms of proposition *AB*

	<i>AaB</i>	<i>AoB</i>	<i>AeB</i>	<i>AiB</i>
1	T	F	F	T
2	F	T	F	T
3	F	T	T	F

We emphasize that terms are non-empty (although we do not disregard empty subclasses) and that this truth table is unconventional. Instead of simple variables, we use categorical propositions. Furthermore, since the entries in each row must be simultaneously satisfied (for both true and false cases), we have eliminated rows that would lead to nonsensical interpretations.

Table 1 delineates the relations of opposition between the categorical forms of proposition *AB*, as follows (*Prior Analytics* II.15; *On Interpretation* 7; Baker, 1977):

- Contrariety. Universal propositions cannot be simultaneously true, but they can be simultaneously false. (We use the opposed conjunction connective, denoted as (\uparrow), which returns false only if both operands are true at the same time):

$$AaB \uparrow AeB$$

- Subcontrariety. Particular propositions cannot be simultaneously false, but they can be simultaneously true:

$$AiB \vee AoB$$

- Contradiction. The universal affirmative and particular negative propositions are contradictory, as are the universal negative and particular affirmative propositions:

$$AaB \leftrightarrow AoB$$

$$AeB \leftrightarrow AiB$$

- Subalternation. The universal affirmative proposition implies the particular affirmative, and the universal negative proposition implies the particular negative:

$$AaB \rightarrow AiB$$

$$AeB \rightarrow AoB$$

Table 1 contains exactly those rows in which all six of the above formulas are simultaneously true. Upon the elimination of inconsistent rows, the application of standard logical connectives enables the expression of the relations of opposition through tautological formulas. In essence, the table is derived directly from the Aristotelian doctrine of oppositions, which *is worded in terms of the possibilities of truth values* (Parsons, 2021: 6).

It is often assumed that truth tables cannot capture the semantics of modal categorical propositions. As a result, the application of modern logical methods to Aristotelian propositions has been limited. In the following sections, we will explore new ways of representing modal expressions, using various combinations of the rows in Table 1 as a tool for logical analysis.

2. The Necessary and the Impossible

In *Prior Analytics* I.13, Aristotle systematically classifies categorical propositions according to their modality, distinguishing between assertoric, necessary, and contingent propositions. He states:

Now, every premise expresses either belonging, or belonging of necessity, or being possible to belong; and some of these, for each prefix respectively, are affirmative and others negative; and of the affirmative and negative premises, in turn, some are universal, some are in part, and some indeterminate (25a1–6). We follow Smith’s translation (1989), although he uses the term “possible” for *endechómenon*, a choice common in many translations of the *Prior Analytics*.

A practical application of this classification is evident in *Prior Analytics* I.14, where Aristotle proves by cases that a certain pattern of reasoning is invalid. First, he rules out the possibility that the conclusion is either an assertoric or a necessary proposition. Then, he explicitly considers the remaining alternative—that the conclusion is contingent—and proceeds to show that this too is impossible.

Aristotle establishes several criteria for creating exclusive oppositions between propositions. A key example is the contradictory opposition between the modality of necessity and that of impossibility, which is highly significant for formalization. By regrouping the rows of Table 1, we can organize them such that, in the column corresponding to the specific categorical form of proposition AB under examination, the rows with a truth value of T are opposed to those with a truth value of F. Under this arrangement, the first group of rows corresponds to the modal concept of necessity (N), while the second group corresponds to what is modally impossible (I).

There are two partitions of this kind:

First Partition: It results from opposing row 1 to rows 2 and 3 in Table 1. This yields the reduced truth table in which the universal affirmative and the particular negative propositions are either necessary or impossible:

Table 2. Necessary (N) and impossible (I) in a-type and o-type propositions

	N(AaB)	I(AaB)	N(AoB)	I(AoB)
1	T	F	F	T
2	F	T	T	F
3	F	T	T	F

Based on the values in Table 2, we can write the following tautological formulas:

$$N(AaB) \leftrightarrow I(AoB)$$

$$I(AaB) \leftrightarrow N(AoB)$$

Second partition: It arises by opposing rows 1 and 2 to row 3. The result is the reduced truth table in which the universal negative and the particular affirmative propositions are either necessary or impossible:

Table 3. Necessary (N) and impossible (I) in e-type and i-type propositions

	N(AeB)	I(AeB)	N(AiB)	I(AiB)
1	F	T	T	F
2	F	T	T	F
3	T	F	F	T

The logical equivalences derived from the values in Table 3 are as follows:

$$N(AeB) \leftrightarrow I(AiB)$$

$$I(AeB) \leftrightarrow N(AiB)$$

3. The Contingent

To identify the modal extension of what is admissible or contingent (C) based on the truth values that categorical propositions can take, we will rely on Aristotle's discussion in *Prior Analytics* I.13:

I use the expressions 'to be possible [*endechómenon*]' and 'what is possible [*endechómenon*]' in application to something if it is not necessary but nothing impossible will result if it is put as being the case (for it is only equivocally that we say that what is necessary is possible). [That this is what is possible is evident from opposed pairs of denials and affirmations. For 'it is not possible to belong' and 'it is impossible to belong' and 'it is necessary not to belong' are either the same or follow one another, and thus their opposites 'it is possible to belong,' 'it is not impossible to belong,' and 'it is not necessary not to belong' will also either be the same or follow from one another (for either the affirmation or the denial is true of everything). Therefore, what is possible will not be necessary and what is not necessary will be possible.] (32a18–29).

We know that the partitions made in Tables 2 and 3 are the only ones that form disjoint sets, in which the truth values T are completely separated from the truth values F for each type of categorical proposition. This characteristic has allowed us to establish their correspondence with the modal concepts of necessity (N) and impossibility (I), respectively. Furthermore, we must consider not-contingent propositions ($\neg C$) alongside necessary and impossible propositions in the columns of those tables. Therefore, we will need to undo those partitions to find alternative regroupings of the rows in Table 1 that yield not-necessary ($\neg N$) and not-impossible ($\neg I$) categorical propositions.

In the tables we have been constructing, each entry is compatible with the other entries in the same row. The way in which contingent propositions are inverted provides us with precise information on how to regroup the rows of Table 1. Following the quoted text, Aristotle explains that each contingent universal proposition can be inverted into its contrary, although the way he justifies this is controversial (Ross, 1957: 327–328; Smith, 1989: 125–126; Striker, 2009: 128–130). Additionally, he extends his argument to the case of particular propositions, which also invert with one another:

It follows that all premises about being possible [*endechómenon*] convert with each other. I do not mean that affirmative premises convert with negatives, but rather that such as have an affirmative form convert with respect to their opposite: that is, ‘possible [*endechómenon*] to belong’ converts to ‘possible not to belong,’ ‘possible to belong to every’ converts to ‘possible to belong to no’ (or ‘not to every’), and ‘it is possible to belong to some’ converts to ‘it is possible not to belong to some.’ It is also the same way in the other cases. For since what is possible is not necessary, and it is possible for what is not necessary not to belong, it is evident that, if it is possible for A to belong to B, then it is also possible for it not to belong; and, if it is possible for it to belong to everyone, then it is also possible for it not to belong to everyone. And it will also be the same in the case of particular affirmations (for the demonstration is the same) (32a28–32b1).

Universal contingent propositions and particular contingent propositions must be considered separately.

In order for the universal propositions to share the same truth values and acquire a contingent value, we must use the modal extensions in which they are not-impossible, joining them by means of inclusive disjunction: $\neg I(AaB) \vee \neg I(AeB)$ (one may also use the inclusive disjunction in which the universal proposition is not-impossible and its subaltern is not-necessary: $\neg I(AaB) \vee \neg N(AiB)$, $\neg I(AeB) \vee \neg N(AoB)$):

Table 4. Contingent (C) propositions of a-type and e-type

	$\neg I(AaB)$	$\neg I(AeB)$	$\neg I(AaB) \vee \neg I(AeB)$	$C(AaB)$	$C(AeB)$
1	T	F	T	T	T
2	F	F	F	F	F
3	F	T	T	T	T

From Table 4 we obtain the equivalence:

$$C(AaB) \leftrightarrow C(AeB)$$

Similarly, when we connect the modally not-impossible particular propositions by means of inclusive disjunction, we obtain the corresponding contingent propositions (as in the previous case, one could also use the not-necessary superalterns):

Table 5. Contingent (C) propositions of i-type and o-type

	$\neg I(AiB)$	$\neg I(AoB)$	$\neg I(AiB) \vee \neg I(AoB)$	$C(AiB)$	$C(AoB)$
1	T	F	T	T	T
2	T	T	T	T	T
3	F	T	T	T	T

From Table 5 we obtain the equivalence:

$$C(AiB) \leftrightarrow C(AoB)$$

In the inversion of particular contingent propositions, it is important to keep in mind that the propositions AiB and AoB are simultaneously true in row 2 insofar as they refer to distinct elements within class B .

These equivalences will be essential for understanding the conversion rules of contingent propositions in Section 6.

4. The Conversion of Assertoric Categorical Propositions

Table 1 can be expanded by incorporating the truth values corresponding to proposition BA , which is obtained by interchanging the subject and predicate in AB . Once logical incongruities in interpretation have been eliminated, the number of rows to consider when including the conversion is reduced to five. The values for the categorical forms of AB are doubled in some rows, resulting in alternative choices that depend on the compatible values in BA :

Table 6. Truth values of the categorical forms of proposition AB and its converse BA

	AaB	AeB	AiB	AoB	BaA	BeA	BiA	BoA
1	T	F	T	F	T	F	T	F
2	T	F	T	F	F	F	T	T
3	F	F	T	T	T	F	T	F
4	F	F	T	T	F	F	T	T
5	F	T	F	T	F	T	F	T

The reader can verify these relationships using simple Venn diagrams (Grennan 1985), keeping in mind that empty terms are not allowed.

Aristotle explains the conversion of assertoric propositions in *Prior Analytics* I.2:

It is necessary for a universal privative premise of belonging to convert with respect to its terms. For instance, if no pleasure is a good, neither will any good be a pleasure [$AeB \leftrightarrow BeA$]. And the positive premise necessarily converts, though not universally but in part. For instance, if every pleasure is a good, then some good

will be a pleasure [$AaB \rightarrow BiA$]. Among the particular premises, the affirmative must convert partially (for if some pleasure is a good, then some good will be a pleasure [$AiB \leftrightarrow BiA$]), but the privative premise need not (for it is not the case that if man does not belong to some animal, then animal will not belong to some man) (25a7–13).

We have inserted the formalization of the conversions in brackets within the text. These are the following logical expressions:

$$(1) \quad AeB \leftrightarrow BeA$$

$$(2) \quad AaB \rightarrow BiA$$

$$(3) \quad AiB \leftrightarrow BiA$$

These expressions are tautologies according to the truth values from Table 6 (in which inconsistent rows were eliminated). Aristotle uses these logical principles of conversion to demonstrate the validity of arguments he calls “imperfect.” For example, he employs (1) in the second figure (*Prior Analytics* I.5) and (2) and (3) in the third figure (*Prior Analytics* I.6; 11).

In the passage cited above, the conversion of the particular negative proposition is denied. The truth tables for AoB and BoA are different. However, at the end of the chapter, an alternative formula seems to be suggested:

But if A does not belong to some B, it is not necessary for B also not to belong to some A (for example if B is animal and A man: for man does not belong to every animal, but animal belongs to every man) (25a23–26; cf. 53a12–14).

This can be formalized as:

$$(4) \quad (AoB \leftrightarrow BoA) \leftrightarrow (AoB \leftrightarrow BaA)$$

Of course, the following also holds:

$$(5) \quad AeB \rightarrow BoA$$

To understand the relationships between categorical propositions and the validity of syllogisms, it is essential to define the notions of logical dependence and independence in terms of truth value combinations (see, e.g., Baker, 1977: 165–166). By introducing a third term, C , alongside A and B , a systematic study of the relationships among the resulting categorical propositions becomes possible. The validity of a syllogism is determined by the logical dependence relationships established between the conjunction of the premises and the conclusion.

5. The Conversion of Necessary Categorical Propositions

Aristotle addresses the conversion of necessary modal propositions at the beginning of *Prior Analytics* I.3:

It will also be the same way in the case of necessary premises: the universally privative premise converts universally, while each kind of affirmative premise

converts partially. For if it is necessary for A to belong to no B, then it is necessary for B to belong to no A (for if it is possible [*endechómenon*] for it to belong to some, then it would be possible [*endechómenon*] for A to belong to some B). And if A belongs to every or to some B of necessity, then it is necessary for B to belong to some A (for if it is not necessary, then neither would A belong to some B of necessity). But a particular privative premise does not convert, for the same reason as that which we also stated earlier (25a27–36).

As we saw, the delimitation of the necessary and the impossible involves considering the partitions that separate the truth values in which the categorical proposition is necessary (because it is true) from the truth values in which it is impossible (because it is false). We only need to apply this idea in Table 6 to formalize the conversion principles that Aristotle presents in the text.

The categorical forms of types *e* and *i* are contradictory, which facilitates their representation with the necessary and impossible operators in the same table:

Table 7. Conversion of necessary *e*-type and *i*-type categorical forms of proposition AB

	N(AeB)	I(AeB)	N(AiB)	I(AiB)	N(BeA)	I(BeA)	N(BiA)	I(BoA)
1	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
2	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
3	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
4	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
5	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T

From Table 7, two rules of conversion for necessary categorical propositions are evident:

$$(1) \quad N(AeB) \leftrightarrow N(BeA)$$

$$(2) \quad N(AiB) \leftrightarrow N(BiA)$$

Principle (1) is used, for example, in the reasoning of the second figure (*Prior Analytics* I.10), while principle (2) is used in the third figure (*Prior Analytics* I.11).

If we finally construct the table for necessary and impossible categorical propositions of types *a* and *o*, we can verify that they are not convertible:

Table 8. Necessary and impossible in *a*-type- and *o*-type categorical forms of proposition AB and its converse

	N(AaB)	I(AaB)	N(AoB)	I(AoB)	N(BaA)	I(BaA)	N(BoA)	I(BoA)
1	T	F	F	T	T	F	F	T
2	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F
3	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T
4	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
5	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F

When AaB is true, BaA can be false. The necessary universal affirmative proposition is therefore not convertible. For similar reasons, the necessary particular negative proposition is also not convertible.

In the cited passage, Aristotle states a third rule or law of conversion in which he does incorporate the universal affirmative:

$$(3) \quad N(AaB) \rightarrow N(BiA)$$

This can be verified as a tautology from the data in Tables 7 and 8. Although there is some indeterminacy between the initial and final lines of the text, the formulation proposed in (3) is the one Aristotle later uses in *Prior Analytics* I.11, in the reasonings of the third figure. In the same tables, it is also observed that $N(AeB)$ does not imply $N(BoA)$, which is consistent with Aristotle's denial of the conversion of the particular negative.

6. The Conversion of Contingent Categorical Propositions

Aristotle dedicates much of *Prior Analytics* I.3 to establishing the principles of conversion for contingent propositions:

When it comes to possible [*endechómenon*] premises, since 'to be possible [*endechómenon*]' is said in several ways (i.e., we say of what is necessary, of what is not necessary, and of what is potential [*dynatón*] that it is possible), the situation with respect to conversion will be the same in all these cases with the affirmatives. For if it is possible for A to belong to every or to some B, then it will be possible for B to belong to some A: for if it is possible for it to belong to none, then neither will it be possible for A to belong to any B (this has been shown earlier). [...] But those which are said to be possible because of being so for the most part or being naturally so (which is the way that we define what is possible) will not be the same in privative conversions. Instead, the universally privative premise does not convert, and the particular premise does convert (25a37–25b3; 25b14–18).

As previously discussed, the contingent is a derived operator that requires considering the inclusive disjunction of the contrary or subcontrary propositions, as the case may be, both modally not-impossible ($\neg I(AaB) \vee \neg I(AeB)$, $\neg I(AiB) \vee \neg I(AoB)$). Particular contingent propositions invert with each other; likewise, universal contingent propositions invert with each other. We now construct their respective conversion tables separately.

The reduced truth table corresponding to the conversion of particular contingent propositions is as follows:

Table 9. Conversion of contingent i-type and o-type categorical forms of proposition AB

	$\neg I(AiB)$	$\neg I(AoB)$	$C(AiB)$	$C(AoB)$	$\neg I(BiA)$	$\neg I(BoA)$	$C(BiA)$	$C(BoA)$
1	T	F	T	T	T	F	T	T
2	T	F	T	T	T	T	T	T
3	T	T	T	T	T	F	T	T
4	T	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
5	F	T	T	T	F	T	T	T

The truth values in Table 9 can be expressed in two conversion principles that coincide with those stated in the Aristotelian text:

$$C(AiB) \leftrightarrow C(BiA)$$

$$C(AoB) \leftrightarrow C(BoA)$$

We gather in a final table the universal contingent categorical forms of proposition *AB*:

Table 10. Contingent a-type and e-type categorical forms of proposition AB

	$\neg I(AaB)$	$\neg I(AeB)$	$C(AaB)$	$C(AeB)$	$\neg I(BaA)$	$\neg I(BeA)$	$C(BaA)$	$C(BeA)$
1	T	F	T	T	T	F	T	T
2	T	F	T	T	F	F	F	F
3	F	F	F	F	T	F	T	T
4	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
5	F	T	T	T	F	T	T	T

Table 10 shows that the universal negative contingent proposition is not convertible, as indicated in the cited Aristotelian passage.

According to Tables 9 and 10, the conversion by accident (or partial conversion) of the universal affirmative contingent proposition into the particular affirmative contingent proposition holds, a principle accepted by Aristotle. Although he does not state it explicitly in the passage, the same principle must be extended to the corresponding negative contingent forms, which exhibit identical truth values.

7. The Possible and the Not-Possible

The study of the interrelations among the various modal categorical propositions requires introducing the notions of the possible (P) and the not-possible ($\neg P$). In the domain of the contingent, the possible is identified with the not-impossible, and, in turn, the not-possible is identified with the not-necessary. When negating the contingent, the possible is identified with the necessary and the not-possible with the impossible. These relations are compatible because contingency and not-contingency are modal values derived from the relation between an affirmative proposition and a negative one.

In Tables 11 and 12, truth values have been assigned directly to the conjunctions that reflect the sense in which the possible and the not-possible must be interpreted depending on the domain in which we find ourselves: whether that of the contingent (Table 11) or that of the not-contingent (Table 12). We have started from Table 1 and transferred to it the truth values associated with the different modal interpretations of the categorical propositions. Each column of the tables presents the conjunction of two modal propositions, thus avoiding confusion about the sense in which the possible and the not-possible are to be interpreted in each case.

The differentiation between the spheres of the contingent and the not-contingent separates modal propositions that, by their truth values, belong to the same equivalence class. If the incongruities between the two spheres are not taken into account, contradictions are inevitable (Łukasiewicz, 1957: 133; Hintikka, 1973: 141; Striker, 2022: 34).

Table 11. Reduced truth table of the conjunction of the possible and the not-impossible, and of the not-possible and the not-necessary, for each categorical form of proposition AB

	P(AaB)	¬P(AaB)	P(AoB)	¬P(AoB)	P(AeB)	¬P(AeB)	P(AiB)	¬P(AiB)
	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧
	¬I(AaB)	¬N(AaB)	¬I(AoB)	¬N(AoB)	¬I(AeB)	¬N(AeB)	¬I(AiB)	¬N(AiB)
1	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F
2	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
3	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T

Considering the truth values in Table 11, the contingent can be expressed by means of the following inclusive disjunctions:

$$C(AiB) \equiv C(AoB) \equiv (P(AiB) \wedge \neg I(AiB)) \vee (P(AoB) \wedge \neg I(AoB)) \equiv (\neg P(AeB) \wedge \neg N(AeB)) \vee (\neg P(AaB) \wedge \neg N(AaB))$$

$$C(AaB) \equiv C(AeB) \equiv (P(AaB) \wedge \neg I(AaB)) \vee (P(AeB) \wedge \neg I(AeB)) \equiv (\neg P(AoB) \wedge \neg N(AoB)) \vee (\neg P(AiB) \wedge \neg N(AiB))$$

In a similar way, we obtain the truth values with which the not-contingent is organized:

Table 12. Reduced truth table of the conjunction of the possible and the necessary, and of the not-possible and the impossible, for each categorical form of proposition AB

	P(AaB)	¬P(AaB)	P(AoB)	¬P(AoB)	P(AeB)	¬P(AeB)	P(AiB)	¬P(AiB)
	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧	∧
	N(AaB)	I(AaB)	N(AoB)	I(AoB)	N(AeB)	I(AeB)	N(AiB)	I(AiB)
1	T	F	F	T	F	T	T	F
2	F	T	T	F	F	T	T	F
3	F	T	T	F	T	F	F	T

The formulas corresponding to the not-contingent are expressed by means of conjunctions:

$$\neg C(AiB) \equiv \neg C(AoB) \equiv (P(AeB) \wedge N(AeB)) \wedge (P(AaB) \wedge N(AaB)) \equiv (\neg P(AiB) \wedge I(AiB)) \wedge (\neg P(AoB) \wedge I(AoB))$$

$$\neg C(AaB) \equiv \neg C(AeB) \equiv (P(AoB) \wedge N(AoB)) \wedge (P(AiB) \wedge N(AiB)) \equiv (\neg P(AaB) \wedge I(AaB)) \wedge (\neg P(AeB) \wedge I(AeB))$$

It is worth noting that the formula $C(AiB)$ is a tautology given the definition of contingency as an inclusive disjunction. (From the values in Table 11, it can be verified that for every row, at least one of the disjuncts in the definition of $C(AiB)$ is true). Its contradictory, $\neg C(AiB)$, is a contradiction. In contrast, both $C(AaB)$ and its contradictory

$\neg C(AaB)$ are contingent formulas. The same considerations extend to the other logically equivalent formulas.

A special case, which requires separate treatment elsewhere, is that of singular propositions. The fact that these propositions refer to individual subjects requires different reductions in their truth table, which in turn determine the need to adapt the model of modal categorical propositions that we have presented.

The previous analysis has assumed that propositions are expressed in a fully quantified logical language. However, natural language often presents semantically indefinite propositions that lack explicit quantifiers. Before concluding, a clarification should be added regarding the formalization of natural language in Aristotelian modal logic. A related issue concerns the proposition “*Logs (B) are white (A)*”, which is semantically indefinite because the natural language expression lacks an explicit quantifier. This means it admits two non-equivalent interpretations in terms of truth values: it is true if “*All logs are white*” ($AiB \wedge AaB$, true only in row 1 of Table 1) and, alternatively, it is true if “*Some logs are white and some logs are not white*” ($AiB \wedge AoB$, true exclusively in row 2 of Table 1). In semantically indefinite propositions, the actual domain of application is not specified; therefore, they can be assimilated to Aristotelian particulars, which neither imply nor exclude universality (*Topics* III.6; *Prior Analytics* I.4–6; Matía Cubillo 2025).

This semantic indefiniteness becomes particularly relevant when we consider terms that may be empty. Aristotle offers as an illustrative example the proposition just examined, that “*Logs are white*” (*Prior Analytics* I.46). By adding the assumption that logs “do not exist,” that proposition must be modally modified in order to remain meaningful: “*It is not-possible that some logs are white*” ($\neg P(AiB)$), or, equivalently, “*It is possible that no log is white*” ($P(AeB)$):

$$\neg P(AiB) \leftrightarrow P(AeB)$$

Depending on whether we interpret the sphere in which we are operating as contingent or not-contingent, the appropriate conjunctions from Tables 11 and 12 (e.g., $\neg P(AiB) \wedge \neg N(AiB)$ for the contingent sphere, or $\neg P(AiB) \wedge I(AiB)$ for the non-contingent sphere) may be added to either side of the equivalence.

8. Conclusion

The construction of truth tables for assertoric categorical propositions has allowed us to identify patterns in their truth values, providing formal criteria for distinguishing modal propositions. The rows of these truth tables can be organized according to different criteria, generating configurations appropriate for modal operators.

It is possible to oppose the set of rows in which a given categorical proposition is true—and therefore necessary—to the rows in which it is false—and consequently impossible. Likewise, a connection can be established by means of inclusive disjunction between a modally not-impossible categorical proposition and its contrary or subcontrary, as the case may be, also not-impossible (or with its subaltern or superaltern, depending on the case, modally not-necessary), thereby obtaining the contingent expression of the given proposition. The opposition between the contingent and the not-contingent is of particular relevance in Aristotelian logic.

Remaining tasks include the adaptation of modal operators to Aristotelian propositions with singular terms, and, in a broader sense, the application of reduced truth tables to the examination of syllogisms with modal propositions. It would be particularly

interesting to develop a logical system that integrates the Aristotelian modal concepts analyzed, verifying the internal consistency of the system and evaluating its deductive capacity. This approach will allow for a deeper understanding of Aristotelian modal logic and its applicability in contemporary contexts.

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